

Design of a Small Field Mill Network for Cloud Modelling

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Abstract— This study focuses on monitoring atmospheric discharge events using a network of electric field mills (EFMs). The EFMs, specifically Campbell Scientific CS110 models, were deployed in the Utah desert, USA, to measure static electric fields. Data collection utilized an Internet of Things (IoT) architecture with MQTT protocol for remote data transmission, enhancing efficiency and reliability. The study demonstrated the effectiveness of this approach in capturing real-time electric field data during thunderstorms, correlating these measurements with lightning location system (LLS) data. Key findings include temporal patterns of electric field variations corresponding to lightning activity, and highlighting significant peaks during storm events. Future research aims to develop a storm cloud model based on integrated data from EFMs and LLS.

Keywords— Atmospheric electric field. Internet of Things (IoT). MQTT. Remote measurement. Atmospheric discharges.

I. INTRODUCTION

Monitoring local environment is crucial for understanding the challenges posed by climate change and its potential responses. These alterations can have significant impacts on the environment, affecting ecosystems, biodiversity, water resources, and human health [1]. Currently, climate parameter observations are conducted using intelligent systems that collect data by measuring various physical parameters in the atmosphere without human intervention [2].

An important parameter for monitoring electrical storms is the electrostatic field. Electrostatic field sensors, known as "field mills" or EFMs (Electric Field Mills), operate based on electrostatic induction and can be cylindrical or disk-shaped. They consist of two metal plates that rotate in an electric field, inducing different electrical potentials and generating an alternating current that is amplified and recorded. Their main advantage is the ability, when calibrated, to infer the magnitude and polarity of charges within thunderclouds [3]. New versions of these systems utilize Internet of Things (IoT) technology to store and provide access to measured data to users anytime and anywhere [4]-[6].

In this context, this study presents the design of a data collection system using the Campbell Scientific CS110 EFM model, which is not originally equipped with IoT. We developed an automatic electric field measurement system deployed in the Utah desert, USA, under the collaboration among the Federal Center for Technological Education of Minas Gerais (CEFET-MG), the National Institute for Space Research (INPE) and Loyola University of Chicago.

It is expected that this measurement system will significantly contribute to projects conducted at the Laboratory of Electromagnetic Transients (LabTEM/CEFET-MG), including lightning measurements, development of intelligent systems for measuring transient currents, among others [7]-[10].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, the main theoretical references that guided the development of this research are presented.

A. Bidirectional Leader Theory

The bidirectional leader theory with zero net charge is currently the most discussed topic regarding the initiation and propagation of lightning leaders. Introduced by Heinz Kasemir in the 1950s, this theory gained experimental evidence from the observation of aircraft-triggered lightning. According to the theory, lightning initiation in an electrified cloud occurs bidirectionally, maintaining a net zero total charge [11]. The bidirectional initiation of lightning applies to various types, including intra-cloud, cloud-to-ground, aircraft-triggered, and rocket-triggered lightning. In this process, lightning propagates in two opposite directions from an origin point, with opposite charges moving in contrary directions, resulting in the observed zero net charge.

B. Thunderstorm Cloud Model

The tripolar thunderstorm cloud model divides the cloud into three distinct regions according to the polarity of the

stored charges: the upper and lower regions contain positive charges, while the intermediate region contains negative charges. The intra-cloud and cloud-to-ground discharge processes initiate with the propagation of the leader channel, with the primary difference between the two processes being the leader's path [12]. In intra-cloud discharge, the bidirectional leader originates between the upper positive charge center and the negative one, developing in both directions with zero net charge, while the electric field sustains the phenomenon. In cloud-to-ground discharges, the process starts similarly to intra-cloud discharges, but the bidirectional channel initiates between the negative charge center and the lower positive one, and it propagates while accumulating charges at the tips and intensifying the local electric field. This promotes propagation in both directions (maintaining zero net charge) and creates a discharge channel that connects the cloud to the ground.

C. Lightning Location Systems

Lightning location systems (LLS) are based on the detection of electromagnetic radiation emitted by lightning, using radio frequencies (RF). These electromagnetic emissions occur as short-duration pulses due to the rapid acceleration of electrons in the lightning channel. Meanwhile, optical emissions result from the excitation or ionization of gases by the electron flow in the lightning channel [13].

D. Embedded Systems

Embedded systems are computational systems that integrate hardware and software into a single device designed to perform specific functions. They utilize components such as microcontrollers, sensors, and actuators while efficiently managing space and resource limitations. These systems are known for their simplified approach, aiming for cost-effectiveness and efficiency [14]. The applications of embedded systems span a wide range of sectors, including security, healthcare, transportation, and consumer electronics, automating tasks with precision and reliability. As technology advances, these systems play a crucial role in contemporary society, driving innovation in various fields, from industrial automation to the Internet of Things and artificial intelligence [15].

E. ESP32s IDE Dual Core

The ESP32s is a low-cost, low-power microcontroller developed by Espressif Systems, primarily designed for Internet of Things (IoT) applications and embedded systems. One of its main features is its integrated Wi-Fi connectivity, which allows the device to easily connect to wireless networks, facilitating communication with cloud servers and other IoT devices. It also offers a wide range of communication interfaces, including UART, SPI, I2C, and GPIO, enabling connection with a variety of sensors and external devices [16]. Equipped with a dual-core 32-bit processor, 520 KB of RAM, and 4 MB of flash memory, the ESP32s has a total of 30 input and output pins, providing flexibility in interfacing with other devices. Its operating voltage is 3.3 V, with power supply options ranging from 7 to 12 V. The chip supports operating

temperature conditions from -40°C to 85°C , making it suitable for implementation in a wide range of environments and industrial applications [17].

F. MQTT Protocol

The Internet of Things (IoT) has revolutionized our interaction with everyday devices, from smart homes to automated industrial environments, promising significant transformations in various aspects of our lives. As the number of devices in IoT networks grows, the need for efficient communication systems becomes crucial. In this context, the MQTT (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport) protocol stands out. Developed in 1999 by Andy Stanford-Clark of IBM and Arlen Nipper of Arcom, initially for pipeline monitoring, MQTT has gained popularity in the IoT world due to its simplicity, efficiency, and reliability [18][19].

MQTT is a lightweight, binary messaging protocol that is easy to implement on the client side. These characteristics make it ideal for devices with limited resources and bandwidth-constrained environments, common in IoT. A distinctive feature of MQTT is its publish-subscribe model, where devices publish messages to specific topics and other devices subscribe to these topics to receive relevant messages [20][21].

Communication between devices is mediated by a central component called a broker. The broker receives messages from publishing devices and delivers them to subscribing devices according to their topic interests. This distributed and scalable architecture of MQTT enables efficient and reliable communication among devices in an IoT network, providing a solid foundation for implementing intelligent and connected systems [22].

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The electric field measurement system is installed in the Utah desert, USA. This system consists of four Campbell Scientific field mills, model CS-110, connected to microcontrollers responsible for reading and transmitting data. Fig. 1 shows the geographical location of the four stations and the distances between them, each meter covering a range of 40 km. Data reception and storage are performed by a 4G modem, enabling remote connectivity. The system is powered by a photovoltaic panel that charges a 12 V battery through a frequency inverter. The installation uses mechanical fastening components to ensure the correct assembly and operation of the station.

The Campbell Scientific CS110 Field Mill is an atmospheric electric field sensor that measures the static electric field in volts per meter (V/m). It communicates through the CR1000 datalogger, which receives data from the sensor and organizes it into a continuous table using the CRBasic programming language developed by Campbell Scientific.

The CS-110 is calibrated by the manufacturer CAMPBELL using the parallel plate method. In this method, a uniform electric field is generated by applying a voltage between the parallel plates. Each EFM sensor is calibrated with the electric

field measurement window facing upwards. A linear adjustment of the calibration data results in a linear calibration equation, with an estimated accuracy of 1% for the sensor calibrated by the parallel plate method.

Fig. 1 Location and range of EFMs

Ideally, for accurate atmospheric electric field readings, the EFM sensor should be installed level with the ground and with the measurement window facing upwards. However, this installation is impractical as it could contaminate the EFM's conductive plates and insulators with water, debris, and insects. Therefore, a configuration is adopted where the EFM is installed with the measurement window facing downwards and elevated to a height of 2 to 3 meters from the ground in long-term operational applications. This inversion of the EFM reduces the effective gain, while the elevation of the sensor increases the gain relative to the ideal geometry with the sensor face upwards. A site correction factor is necessary to adjust the factory multiplier f , making the electric field corrected by a unique linear factor for each sensor.

The equipment is fully shielded against atmospheric disturbances, along with the power supply cables, and the system is properly grounded. These measures ensure the system's integrity and the accuracy of the collected data, even in the presence of strong electromagnetic disturbances.

The CR1000 has an internal memory of 4 MB, capable of recording periodic measurements every second, resulting in 87,885 measurements. This would fill the memory in three days, necessitating daily manual data collection. To avoid this, an embedded system was implemented to facilitate communication between the sensors and the data processing center, using an Internet of Things (IoT) architecture. Fig. 2 presents the operational topology of the electric field measurement station.

The system presented involves data acquisition using the CR1000 datalogger, which communicates data through a serial interface with the ESP32s microcontroller, acting as an intermediary between transmitted and received data to the processing center. The UART serial interface enables

communication between the ESP32s microcontroller and the CR1000 data logger, ensuring data transmission integrity and accuracy. The microcontroller is responsible for sending received data to the processing system.

We opted for wireless connectivity to facilitate communication with systems in open-field environments, selecting the MQTT protocol, which offers an efficient and scalable solution for data transmission in IoT environments. Its lightweight and simplicity result in low network overhead, ensuring fast and reliable communication between the embedded system and the IoT server. Additionally, it allows adjusting the message delivery assurance level as per system requirements. The MQTT publish/subscribe architecture facilitates the implementation of a flexible and modular messaging system, suitable for dynamic and distributed environments. A PCB was designed to power and mount the ESP32s.

Fig. 2 Operational Topology in Communication

Data acquisition was performed using Campbell's proprietary software, Loggernet, which provides a reliable and robust platform for automated data collection and management. Its intuitive interface allows easy configuration of data acquisition devices, such as weather station dataloggers, simplifying the process of data collection and organization into various formats and units of measurement. Loggernet offers advanced programming and scheduling features, enabling the automation of data collection tasks at specific time intervals. Its integration capability with data processing and analysis systems is also noteworthy.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The electronic device developed to enable remote connection with the CS 110 and the user was initially tested in a controlled environment and subsequently in an open field. Both tests confirmed that the device operated within expected standards, providing a viable solution for remote data collection. Fig. 1 shows the finalized device, and Fig. 4 presents the CS 110 installed in the field.

After the installation of the electric field meters, the system has remained operational since March 17, 2024, enabling continuous collection of electric field data in the region. Fig. 5 presents the electric field values recorded by the four field mills during a storm occurring between 21:30 and 23:30 on March 20.

LLS data from the same region, as shown in Fig. 6 and collected during the same storm, indicate that most lightning strikes occurred outside the measurement area of the field mills (within a 40 km radius). In the graphs, 'x' symbols represent cloud-to-ground discharges, and '*' symbols indicate intra-cloud discharges. This result was expected due to the nature of measurements obtained by field mills, which show slower variations over time due to the movement of charge centers within storm clouds.

Fig. 2 Finalized device

Fig. 4 CS 110 installed in the field

Fig. 5 Electric field measured at the 4 field mills

Fig. 6 Atmospheric discharges on March 20

Between June 26 and 27, we conducted extensive data collection on atmospheric discharges in the region. The data in Fig. 7 were collected by the LLS between 21:30 on June 26 and 07:10 on June 27, near the electric field measurement stations. In this analysis, events are not limited to the area covered by the field mill stations. Due to the significant amount of data during this period, it was divided into three distinct periods: the first from 21:30 on June 26 to 01:00 on June 27; the second from 01:30 to 03:15 on June 27; and the third from 03:38 to 07:10 on June 27.

Fig. 7 Atmospheric discharges between June 26 and 27.

Fig. 8 shows an enlarged image of the electric field values measured at the EFMs between 21:30 on June 26 and 01:00 on June 27. In Fig. 9, we present the data obtained from the LLS for intra-cloud and cloud-to-ground discharges within the ranges of the three electric field measurement stations. By correlating these two figures, it is evident that the initial peaks in electric field occur near EFM3, which aligns with the observation that most lightning strikes initially occur within EFM3's range. As the charge center moves, it approaches the other EFMs, and subsequent discharges are noted within their ranges.

During the first peak in electric field, approximately 4 kV/m was recorded, with the highest peak current value for cloud-to-ground discharges observed by the LLS reaching 16.3 kA. It is noteworthy that around midnight, there was a high frequency of lightning strikes near the measurement stations, resulting in fluctuations in the electric fields. At this time, the EFMs recorded the highest electric field amplitudes, with the highest peak current value observed by the LLS reaching 35.4 kA, and a maximum of 8 kV/m observed at EFM1.

Fig. 8 Electric field from the 3 field mills in the first interval.

Fig. 9 Atmospheric discharges in the first interval.

As shown in Fig. 10, during the second interval, most events occurred at the edges of the EFMs' range. These events were likely caused by charge centers from previous events observed in the first interval of analysis. Notably, the cloud moved southeast, following the direction of the initial discharges recorded in this period. During this interval, the maximum peak current observed by the LLS was 32.3 kA, recorded at 02:27 within the coverage area of the three EFMs. Fig. 11 illustrates the variation of the electric field during this same period, highlighting the greatest variation at EFM1. This

suggests the presence of charge centers moving at the edges of the three field mills' range.

Fig. 10 Atmospheric discharges in the second interval.

Fig. 11 Electric field from the 3 field mills in the second interval.

Figure 12 depicts the incidence of intra-cloud and cloud-to-ground discharges during the third interval. In this period, there wasn't a single region with a significantly higher number of events in isolation; instead, the events occurred dispersedly across the area covered by the 3 EFMs. This suggests that the storm cloud charge centers passed very close to the measurement stations. Correlating Figure 12 with Figure 13, which shows the electric fields observed by the 3 EFMs during the same interval, it is evident that most discharges occurred between 06:00 and 07:00, very close to the measurement stations. During this period, very abrupt oscillations in the electric field readings were also recorded.

Fig. 12 Atmospheric discharges in the third interval.

Fig. 13 Electric field from the 3 field mills in the third interval.

The results underscored the effectiveness of the developed electronic device for remote data collection. Significant correlations were observed between the electric field data measured by the EFMs and the atmospheric discharges detected by the Lightning Location System (LLS), revealing distinct patterns of electrical activity across various temporal intervals during storms. For future studies, we aim to leverage these correlations to propose a storm cloud model. Expanding the network of measurement stations would be essential to enhance the precision and comprehensiveness of our analyses, offering deeper insights into the dynamics of electrical storms in the studied region.

V. CONCLUSION

The electronic device designed for remote data collection has proven to be an efficient and reliable solution. Implementing an Internet of Things (IoT)-based architecture significantly facilitated communication between the sensors and the data processing center, eliminating the need for daily manual data collection. The continuous collection of electric field data since the initial installation and the analysis of data

during storms confirm the device's effectiveness in capturing real-time atmospheric phenomena. Significant correlations between the electric field data measured by the EFMs and the atmospheric discharges detected by the Lightning Location System (LLS) highlight distinct patterns of electrical activity across various temporal intervals during storms. The adoption of IoT and the MQTT protocol ensured data transmission integrity and accuracy, proving this approach suitable for remote monitoring in hard-to-reach areas. This study provides a practical solution for real-time data acquisition and validates the application of modern technologies in advancing meteorological research and improving our understanding of atmospheric discharge dynamics.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to acknowledge the support and resources provided by the Federal Center for Technological Education of Minas Gerais (CEFET-MG) for this research project. Additionally, the authors are grateful for the financial support received from the Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de Minas Gerais (FAPEMIG) through grant number PCE-00106-24.

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